

Sodium alginate and Chitosan aided design of form-stable Polyrotaxane based phase change materials with ultra-high latent heat

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ABSTRACT. We prepared a series of highly porous Polyrotaxane/Sodium alginate, and Polyrotaxane/Chitosan foam alloys according to a sustainable pathway by using water as the only solvent. The foam alloys were further used as supporter materials for Poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG) encapsulation, to fabricate shape-stable bio-based phase change materials (PCMs). The pore morphology and the internal interface between PEG and foam alloys were characterized by scanning electron microscope (SEM). Due to the good compatibility between foam alloys and PEG, the PCM performed perfect anti-leakage properties. The introduction of Sodium alginate or Chitosan ensures the shape stability of the PCMs during the phase transition. The PCMs performed good cycle stability and showed ultra-high latent heat (171.6 J/g -189.5 J/g). Finally, we compared the typical indicators of this work with those reported in the literature, and the comparison highlighted that the present PCMs have the significant advantages: high melting enthalpy, convenient preparation and outstanding sustainability. Notably, the work provided a sustainable idea for the design of anti-leakage and shape-stable PEG-based PCMs.

KEYWORDS: Polyrotaxane, Sodium alginate, Chitosan

Highlights

1. The PCMs have ultra-high latent heat and perfect form stability.
2. The PCM can be fabricated in sustainable process with high efficiency.
3. It expanded the application of Chitosan and Sodium alginate.

1. Introduction

The development of high-performance phase-change materials (PCM) is a practical direction with broad application prospects. With the increasingly prominent "double carbon" and global environmental problems, local governments have proposed corresponding laws and regulations. The development and application of biomass materials and the development of energy-saving and emission-reduction composites are the trend of the era. This will bring the second spring of research on phase change materials, which can be widely used in the building thermal regulation (Saxena et al., 2021, Rathore and Shukla, 2021, Soares et al., 2016) and heat energy storage. (Liu et al., 2022, Kurnia et al., 2022) A typical shape-stable PCM consists of a 3D skeleton and a PCM work substance. (Wang et al., 2022, Li et al., 2022, Xue et al., 2019)

For the 3D skeleton part, more and more scientists have tried various green substrates (such as, Chitosan, (Du et al., 2022, Samoson et al., 2022, Song et al., 2022) Cellulose (Wang et al., 2022, Wu et al., 2022, Zhao et al., 2022) and sodium alginate (Wang et al., 2022, Zhou et al., 2022)) to prepare 3D-foam for the PCM substance encapsulation. For example, Jia et al. fabricated boron nitride (BN)/chitosan (CS) frameworks with three-dimensional (3D) porous structures were fabricated, and effective thermal conductive pathways could be created in the resultant porous materials for PCM encapsulation.(Jia et al., 2020) Cheng et al. fabricated a flexible supporting material with a folded layer-bridge network structure by dispersing carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in acetic acid solution of chitosan with poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) using a directional freezing method. Then chitosan/PVA/CNTs scaffold was infiltrated with polyethylene glycol (PEG) to prepare composite PCM. (Cheng et al., 2020) In addition, the polyethylene glycol (PEG) was in situ-loaded with Ca^{2+} -crosslinked sodium alginate (SA) on the account of the coordination of Ca^{2+} with carboxyl

groups in the SA structure, to produce the bio-based composite PCMs.(Liu et al., 2020)

As well reported, phase change thermal storage technology is an effective approach to solving the mismatch between energy supply and demand. However, this technique requires considerable efforts to the successful application and popularization, which required both the high-performance and eco-friendly manufacturing. In view of designing high-performance form-stable PCMs with desirable latent heat enthalpy, in our previous reports, we found the advantages and disadvantages of PLR supramolecules themselves as phase change materials. (Yin et al., 2021) We achieved the improvement of its function expansion through the further introduction of flame retardants (Yin et al., 2022) and PEG (Yin et al., 2022) to achieve high fire safety or enthalpy optimization of flexible and reprocessible PCM. For further improving the encapsulation ratio of PEG, we envisage that the PLR foam will have a greater absorption potential and the PEO chain of PLR will ensure the perfect compatibility between the foam and the PCM work substance. After brief initial attempts, we found that pure PLR foams tend to collapse during PEG absorption, making it difficult for PCM to retain shape in the end (Figure S1). This may be due to high porosity, imperfect cyclodextrin crystallization, and insufficient physical intersection. In view of the water solubility of PLR, the design principle for the expansion of biomass material functions, we will consider the selection of water-soluble rigid natural macromolecules, such as Chitosan and Sodium Alginate. Both Chitosan and Sodium alginate could be used as a 3D estimation enhancer to achieve high enthalpy values and good compatibility (structural similarity between cyclodextrins and natural polysaccharides). In summary, this study aimed to design different ratios of PLR/Chitosan, PLR/SA-based alloy foams for the encapsulation of PEG, thereby achieving high enthalpy and high shape stability of the PCMs.

2. Experimental

Materials. Poly (ethylene oxide) (PEO) with a weight average molar mass of 9×10^5 g mol⁻¹, α -Cyclodextrin (α -CD, $\geq 99.8\%$) and sodium alginate (SA, with high viscosity) and PEG 6k were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (USA), Chitosan (CH, 200-600 mPas, was purchased from TCI and used as received. Deionized water is made in our laboratory.

Chitosan solution preparation. The chitosan solution (3 % (m/v)) was prepared by mixing chitosan powder as much as 3 grams in 100 mL of distilled water and 2 mL of acetic acid. The solution was stirred for 24 hours.

Sodium Alginate solution preparation. Sodium alginate has a strong affinity with water and care is required to achieve a homogeneous aqueous solution. The SA solution (3 % (m/v)) was prepared by mixing SA powder as much as 3 grams in 100 mL of distilled water. The solution was stirred using a magnetic stirrer overnight.

Synthesis of Polyrotaxane (PLR). PEO (3 g) was dissolved in H₂O (80 mL) at 80 °C, and then α -CD (1.5 g) with different mass ratio 50% was slowly added. After stirring for overnight at room temperature, the reaction mixture was cooled down and kept at 4 °C for 72 h to yield the corresponding inclusion complex solutions. FTIR (cm⁻¹, KBr window) 3340, 2875, 1645, 1466, 1340, 1278, 1240, 1147, 1096, 1056, 1025, 960, 945, 839, 753, 700, 571. The FTIR curve was provided in Figure S1.

Preparation of foam alloys. The formulations are listed in **Table S1**. We mixed PLR solution with different contents of CH and SA of different contents and freeze-dried.

Characterization. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis was performed for each film (5-10 mg) using a TA-Q200 in a N₂ atmosphere (50 mL min⁻¹). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

and EDS were carried out on the apparatus (SEM, EVO MA15, Zeiss) and FIB-FEG SEM dual-beam microscope (FIBFEGEM) (Helios NanoLab 600i, FEI). Prior to the observation, the conductive gold layer was sprayed. Sample PLR-PA20 was selected for cycle stability test (80 cycles). Both heating and cooling procedures were run at $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ to calculate the change of exothermic and endothermic heat as well as the enthalpy efficiency and phase change temperatures. The sample was cut into a disc with a cutter, and then heated at different temperatures ($25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) for the detecting of form stability (leakage or shape change).

3. Results and discussion

Figure 1. (a) Chemical structure of PLR, (b) Chemical structure of Chitosan and Alginate sodium, (c) illustration of 3D foams (Chitosan-PLR foams and SA-PLR foams), (d) Image of selected foam alloy on the leaf to show the lightweight and highly porous nature of the foam, and SEM images correspond to (e) Sodium alginate foam, (f) Chitosan foam, (g) PLR foam, (h) CH 0.1, (i) CH 0.3, (j) CH 0.5, (k) CH 1, (l) SA 0.1, (m) SA 0.3, (n) SA 0.5, and (o) SA1.

PLR-50 was prepared according to our previous work, (Yin et al., 2021) and selected as a representative component to blend with different ratio of SA solution (3 wt.%) and Chitosan solution (3 wt.%), respectively (Figure 1a, 1b). After freeze-drying, the foam alloys as shown in Figures 1c and 1d are obtained. The foam alloys were light weight and highly porous, as listed in Table 1. Specific material preparation details (Table S1) were explained in experimental section in the Supplementary materials, and the preparation parameters, porosities were also listed in **Table 1**. Figures 1e-1o show cross-sectional SEM images of all samples. We can see that the pure SA sample has a larger pore size and microscopically shows a larger and connected open pore structure. Chitosan based foams showed a random morphology, with smaller pore sizes than that of SA foam. Pure PLR has more uniform pore structure and has a relative regular wall thickness. PLR-polysaccharide foams exhibited the key characteristics of SA or CH, respectively. Typically, **Figure 1l-1o** still presents a large sheet-like open-pore structure, while for Figure 1h-1k, the pore size is still relatively small. However, the orderliness of the PLR-CH system is improved compared to that of pure Chitosan. Through SEM images, we can also know that the PLR has good compatibility with both SA and Chitosan, which is mainly due to the chemical similarity between α -CD and Chitosan or Sodium alginate. Accordingly, no phase separation was observed in the SEM section images. The possible reason for this is that PEO and α -CD have structural similarity with polysaccharide and intermolecular hydrogen bonding. Therefore, we believe that the alloy foam is a molecular-level dispersed combination of PLR and Chitosan or SA. This good dispersion will greatly improve the compatibility between the interfaces (PCM substance and supporter), thereby inhibiting the leakage to some extent. In addition, for Chitosan samples, there is a significant shrinkage phenomenon during lyophilization. The porosity of the material can be calculated by Eq.

(1). The corresponding data are listed in Table 1. The porosity of the porous material is measured by Eq (2):(Yin et al., 2016)

$$Porosity\% = \frac{\rho_{bulk} - \rho_{porous}}{\rho_{bulk}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where, ρ_{porous} is the density of porous materials, ρ_{bulk} is the density of bulk polymer and ρ_{PCM} is the density of PCM (after PEG encapsulation). The density values are all calculate and listed in **Table 1**. The efficiency is accordingly calculated and also presented in Table 1.

We can find that the porosities of foam alloys are between 94.65% and 96.47%. Such high porosity can effectively ensure the adsorption and encapsulation efficiency of PCM. The crystallinity ($\varphi_c\%$) were calculated in the second heating run from 0 °C to 100 °C at heating or cooling rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ by Eq. (1):(Yin et al., 2015)

$$\varphi_c\% = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\omega_i \Delta H_m^0} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where, ΔH_m (J g⁻¹) represented the measured enthalpies of PCM, ΔH_m^0 (J g⁻¹) was the melting enthalpy for a 100 % crystalline PEG and ω_i was the fraction of the component i in the sample. The value taken for ΔH_m^0 of PEG was 196.4 J g⁻¹. (Chrissopoulou et al., 2011) The corresponding φ_c (%) are summarized in Table 1. All the samples performed ultra-high crystallinity as high as 87.4%~97.6%. We assign that such high crystallinity may originate from the excellent compatibility of foam alloys with PEG.

Table 1. Basic parameters of the foam alloys and the key values of the PCMs

	ρ_{porous} (g mL ⁻¹)	ρ_{bulk} (g mL ⁻¹)	Porosity (%)	ρ_{PCM} (g mL ⁻¹)	Encapsulation efficiency (%)	Melting enthalpy (J g ⁻¹)	φ_c (%)
PLR	0.0561±0.0023	1.47±0.04	96.18	-	-	-	-
Chitosan	0.0743±0.0035	0.98±0.03	91.40	1.01±0.04	91.65	178.3	90.78
CH-0.1	0.0597±0.0011	1.44±0.04	95.85	1.22±0.02	95.10	184.7	94.04
CH-0.3	0.0664±0.0019	1.39±0.02	95.21	1.13±0.05	94.12	189.5	96.49
CH-0.5	0.0671±0.0013	1.35±0.07	95.02	1.21±0.06	94.45	187.5	95.47
CH-1	0.0681±0.0043	1.27±0.05	94.65	1.09±0.03	93.75	189.1	96.28

SA	0.0263±0.0052	1.21±0.05	97.83	1.19±0.01	97.79	191.7	97.61
SA-0.1	0.0513±0.0071	1.45±0.04	96.47	1.19±0.03	95.69	187.6	95.52
SA-0.3	0.0531±0.0026	1.43±0.03	96.28	1.13±0.01	95.30	177.6	90.43
SA-0.5	0.0535±0.0013	1.40±0.03	96.19	1.12±0.02	95.22	178.4	90.84
SA-1	0.0569±0.0044	1.37±0.05	95.83	1.14±0.01	95.01	171.6	87.37

Figure 2. (a) Illustration of the PEG encapsulation process, (b) the potential interaction between PEG and Chitosan, Sodium Alginate and PLR, (c) SEM images of the Chitosan and chitosan functionalized foam encapsulated PCMs and (d) SEM images of the SA and SA containing foams encapsulated PCM groups.

The foam alloys obtained above was immersed in the melt of PEG6k at 80 °C in vacuum oven overnight, and finally the form-stable PCMs were obtained. The encapsulation process is shown in Figure 2a. Figure 2b illustrates the potential hydrogen bonding interactions between PEG and Chitosan, SA as well as PLR, due to which, the PEG showed good compatibility with the foam alloy supports. Therefore, no obvious interface delamination was found in the SEM images (Figure 2c and Figure 2d). In addition, we found significant PEG spherulites, indicating that the PEG is inside the alloy foams and can crystalline sufficiently. This is another important factor that increase latent heat. Its specific crystallinity data is calculated according to the Eq. 2 and listed in Table 1. Then, we calculated the specific adsorption amount of PEG and the efficiency of encapsulation by Eq. (3):

$$Encapsulation\ Efficiency\ \% = \frac{m_{PCM} - m_{foam}}{m_{PCM}} \times 100\% = \frac{\rho_{PCM} - \rho_{foam}}{\rho_{PCM}} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

where, m_{PCM} and m_{foam} are the weight of the final PCM composited, ρ_{PCM} is the density of the final PCM composites, and ρ_{foam} is the density of the foam.

Figure 3. Form stability test of the samples: (a) PLR/sodium alginate/PEG group, (b) PLR/Chitosan/PEG group: (blue), 25 °C, (red) 80 °C for 2 h, (c) illustration of micromorphology of pure SA and PEG, (d) PLR/Chitosan/PEG and (e) illustration of micromorphology of Chitosan/PEG.

As shown in **Figure 3a**, pure SA sample showed slight leakage. The samples containing PLR (SA-0.1 to SA-1) showed no leakage. The pure Chitosan foam does not show significant leakage. It appears more uniform micro pore morphology in the samples with PLR. As for the possible reason for SA encapsulated PCM leakage (as shown in Figure 3c) was assigned that SA foam has a large open pore structure. In addition, in the chemical structure of SA, the hydroxyl density is also relatively low. PEG in the molten state has a large degree of freedom to move in a large internal gap, which is easy to leak accordingly. For Chitosan containing samples, the pore size is small (comparing with SA foam), and the density of polar groups (2 -OH groups and 1 -NH₂) is higher than that of SA (2 -OH groups in one 6-member-ring), so the leakage resistance is better than that of pure SA series materials (Figure 3e). However, its significant shortcomings are the poor

uniformity of pore size and large size shrinkage during molding and freeze drying (Figure 1f) (with about 5~10 % shrinkage in diameter during free drying). In the new samples with PLR, as shown in Figure 3d, the compatibility between the pore wall and PEG substance itself is improved because PLR is compatible with chitosan or SA in molecular level. Furthermore, because the main molecular chain of PLR is the same as PEG, it can form eutectic, which shows a good space binding effect. Therefore, the leakage resistance has been fully guaranteed and even significantly improved when comparing with the pure SA or pure Chitosan encapsulated samples.

Figure 4. (a) DSC curves of SA-containing PCM samples, (b) DSC curves of CH containing PCMs, (c) latent heat values of the SA-containing PCM samples, (d) latent heat values of the CH-containing

PCMs, (d) cycle performance (the main parameters) of the SA-0.5 as a typical example, (f) cycle performance (DSC curves) of sample SA-0.5, and (g) the comparison of latent heat values between the value in current work and the values from literature elsewhere. (The details for reported values were listed in Table 2.)

Figure 4a and **4b** show the DSC curves of the SA containing samples and Chitosan containing samples, respectively. We present the latent heat, as shown in **Figure 4c** and **4d**. For the SA system, due to the highest porosity and the highest adsorption capacity, it has the highest latent heat (Sample pure SA) with latent heat of 191.75 J g^{-1} . With the addition of PLR, the latent heat decreased due to the change of porosity and micro morphology, but remains at a very high level (higher than 171.6 J g^{-1}). For the Chitosan-containing PCMs, the encapsulation efficiency is relatively low due to the volume shrinkage of the pure Chitosan foam encapsulated samples. After the introduction of the PLR, the porosity increases, so the encapsulation efficiency and enthalpy value also increase. **Figure 4e** and **4f** shows the enthalpy value of the material under nearly 80 cycles, and it can be clearly seen that melting temperature, solidification temperature, melting enthalpy and other indicators remain almost constant, indicating that the materials have good cycle stability during phase change. Furthermore, we conduct a series of comparisons with literature reports, and the performance obtained in this work are the highest. As further shown in Table 2, the recently reported latent heat of phase transition of PEG-based PCM is generally below 160 J g^{-1} . The supporting materials used are mostly petroleum-based compounds; (Shi et al., 2022) (Du et al., 2021) organic solvents are sometimes involved in the preparation process; (Li et al., 2022, Tian et al., 2022) which increase the environmental cost to some extent. In addition, in some reports, the authors directly used inorganic 3D foam as the support materials, (Li and Wang, 2021, Liu et al., 2021) which maybe increase the possibility of leakage due to the difference in interfacial compatibility between PEG and the inorganic micro-nano structure. By the comparison analysis, we claim that the process is simple

and environmentally friendly, so it is a sustainable material research system. The comparison shows that this work has the following significant advantages: (1) high melting enthalpy, (2) convenient preparation and outstanding sustainability.

Figure 5 (a) Honeycomb like PLR foam, (b) disordered pore structure of Chitosan foam, (c) Lotus-leaf-like structure of SA foam, (d) SEM image of sample with both Chitosan and PLR, and (e) the SEM image of sample with both Sodium alginate and PLR.

We know that all the PLR, Chitosan and SA have specific deficiencies in the preparation of foam-encapsulated PEG (**Figure 5**). For example, the Honeycomb-shaped PLR foam (Figure 5a) collapsed during the adsorption process, the foam volume shrinks significantly during the freeze drying of Chitosan foam with low porosity (Figure 5b) accordingly, while the large-pore foam formed by SA (Figure 5c) showed significant leakage during the phase transition process. Fortunately, high-performance encapsulation of PEG can be achieved by blending Polyrotaxane with SA or CH to prepare foam alloys (Figure 5d and 5e). Through comparative analysis, we realized that in the material system, the PLR and the polysaccharide double network in the alloy foams each act as different functional components. The Polyrotaxane optimizes the compatibility of the foam

cell surface with PEG, and the polysaccharide acts as the stereotyped backbone. Therefore, overall, the double network alloy systems have excellent comprehensive properties. Moreover, the application and promotion of natural macromolecules is in line with the needs of the era of sustainable development.

Table 2. Comparison with the preparation method, key parameters for the PEG based PCMs in the literature elsewhere.

No.	Supporter materials	PCM substance	Preparation method	Solvent used	PEG loading rate (%)	Enthalpy efficiency (%)	Latent heat (J g ⁻¹)	References
1	Chemically cross-linked cellulose nanocrystal	PEG-4000	In-situ synthesis	Water	85.7	95.0	145.8	(Cheng et al., 2022)
2	π - π stacking	PEG-4000	Block copolymerization	Tetrahydrofuran	-	-	72.8-123.4	(Tian et al., 2022)
3	Potatoes/MXene	PEG-6000	Vacuum impregnation	Water	-	91.5-98.3	100.5-139.9	(Fang et al., 2022)
4	Polyimide (PI)/phosphorene (PR) hybrid aerogel	PEG-6000	Vacuum impregnation	-	90.0	97.0	150.0	(Shi et al., 2022)
5	Graphene/cysteamine aerogel	PEG-6000	Vacuum impregnation	Water	98.2	-	159.0	(Yu et al., 2022)
6	Poly(acrylamide-co-acrylic acid) copolymer	PEG-6000	Free radical polymerization	NaOH	89.0	96.1	138.6	(Yang et al., 2022)
7	Polyvinyl alcohol	PEG-2000	Vacuum immersion	boric acid/APP/BN/water	93.0	91.1	163.9	(Zhou et al., 2022)
8	Boron nitride (BN) and Expanded graphite and EP	PEG-4000	Blending and curing	-	54.0	75.1	79.9	(Luo et al., 2022)
9	Halloysite-based FSPCM	PEG-1000	Encapsulate	H ₂ SO ₄ and water	55.0	95.8	82.2	(Gu et al., 2022)
10	Expanded vermiculite/-boron nitride	PEG 2k	typical vacuum impregnation	EtOH	88.0-97.0	-	37.8-55.3	(Wang et al., 2022)
11	Carbon fibers and polyacrylic acid	PEG-2000	Freeze casting technology	N,N'-methylenebis (acrylamide)	-	-	62.0	(Li et al., 2022)
12	Polyethylene glycol (PEG)/epoxy (EP) resin	PEG-6000	Curing reaction	-	50.0-80.0	-	74.0-96.1	(Wang et al., 2022)

13	Mica	PEG-1000	Vacuum impregnation	-	86.0	98.5	77.7	(Zhang et al., 2022)
14	3D porous TiO ₂	PEG-6000	Physical impregnation	Water/EtOH	92.0	93.3	153.3	(Sun et al., 2021)
15	SiO ₂ network and MWCNTs-COOH	PEG-6000	Sol-gel method	Water	81.0-84.4	-	116.3-133.5	(Yan et al., 2021)
16	Mesoporous carbon FDU-15	PEG	Melting impregnation	EtOH	75.0	71.3	81.8	(Feng et al., 2021)
17	3D metal-organic network	PEG-20000	Hydrogen bonding interaction	Water	98.0	99.0	158.4	(Wang et al., 2021)
18	Melamine foam and MXene	PEF-4000	Vacuum impregnation	Water	98.3	101.3	186.2	(Du et al., 2021)
19	Rice husk ash	PEG-2000	Physical mixing and impregnation process	-	-	-	119.3	(Yu et al., 2021)
20	Nanoporous fumed silica	PEG-2000	Melt spinning technique	EtOH	-	-	119.4	(Xia et al., 2021)
21	Poly (Glycerol-Itaconic acid)	PEG-6000	Polycondensation + BPO curing	-	72.7	67.9	86.9	(Yin et al., 2021)
22	Lignin-modified graphene aerogel	PEG-4000	Vacuum impregnation	Water/EtOH	99.2	98.4	168.7	(Wei et al., 2021)
23	Expanded vermiculite composite	PEG	Physical blending and impregnation	-	-	-	110.7	(Deng, 2021)
24	Chemically treated wood	PEG-4000	Vacuum impregnation	NaOH/Na ₂ S O ₃	-	99.7	132.6	(Liu et al., 2021)
25	Bio-based bamboo flour	PEG-10000	Straightforward dry ball milling	-	70.0	61.1	113.0	(Zheng et al., 2022)
26	Bionic hierarchical porous aluminum nitride ceramic	PEG 2k	-	Water	42.9	-	88.7	(Qiu et al., 2021)
27	Azobenzene-Graphene	PEG	Ultrasound-assisted physically blended	-	95.0	-	86.5	(Li and Wang, 2021)
28	MXene	PEG-6000	Vacuum curing process	-	70.0-90.0	-	83.3-96.8	(Liu et al., 2021)
29	PLR	PEG	Solvent casting	Water	<77.8	>100	116.1-162.2	(Yin et al., 2022)
30	PLR-P foam alloy	PEG	3D foam encapsulation	Water	-	87.4-96.3	171.6-189.5	Current work

4. Conclusions

In order to prepare high-performance 3D form-stable PCM, two kinds of polysaccharides, Chitosan and Sodium alginate were used in this work to modify the form stability of PLR based foam. By adjusting the ratio of PLR to polysaccharides, the pore size and morphology can be regulated. The resulting foams have high porosity (>94.65 %) and high PEG uptake (93.75 %), resulting in the high phase transition enthalpies of 171.6-189.5 J g⁻¹. The PCMs showed outstanding form stability and leakage resistance. In the process, we are gratifying to find that while improving the shape stability of Polyrotaxane by compounding polysaccharides, Polyrotaxane also effectively regulates the practical problems, namely, the leakage of Sodium Alginate foam and the volume shrinkage of chitosan foam. Specifically, Polyrotaxane acts as host and compatibilizer with PEG for ensuring the anti-leakage performance, while Sodium Alginate and chitosan act as dimensional stabilizers to keep the 3D stable shape. Notably, the preparation convenience and the sustainability of materials, and the outstanding performance indicators of PCM are expected to be practically popularized and applied in the field of phase change energy storage.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Guang-Zhong Yin: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Data curation, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing, Project administration. **Xiao-Mei Yang:** Validation, Data curation, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing. **Alba Marta López:** Data curation, Investigation, Writing-review & editing. **Mei-Ting Wang:** Formal analysis, Writing-review & editing. **Wen Ye:** Formal analysis, Writing-review & editing. **Baoyun Xu:** Formal

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Acknowledgment

The authors acknowledge the financial support provided by BIOFIRESAFE Project funded by Ministerio De Ciencia E Innovación (MINECO), Spain with Project number: PID2020-117274RB-I00BIOFIRESAFE.

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